

Deliverable 2.1 - Network Management Group Portfolios

1. Background: Objectives, Milestones, Deliverables and Workplan

1.1. This document addresses the following milestone and deliverable within WP2:

- **D2.1. NMG portfolios:** NMG's portfolio leadership established, together with membership of each portfolio Implementation Group and Terms of Reference (ToR).
- **MS10: NMG and portfolios set up:** Scope, leadership and membership of portfolios finalised; *Modus Operandi* operational

1.2. These contribute to the overall objectives of WP2 which are:

- To implement and establish the proposed (from the current EUPHRESKO-I Project) structure and modus operandi of the long-term self-sustainable Network
- To evaluate and refine the structure and modus operandi of the long-term network of funders to ensure that a strong, long-lasting and self-sustainable network emerges
- To maintain on-going core network activities that underpin trans-national research coordination and collaboration, e.g. mapping activities; dissemination of transnational research outputs; advising on plant health research priorities in FP7; maintaining external linkages; maintaining the EUPHRESKO toolbox.

1.3. The relevant elements of the workplan are detailed below:

WP 2.1. Implement the long-term network leadership & management structure

- The structure and organisation will follow the model and principles developed in the original EUPHRESKO-I Project for a self-sustainable network that can implement EUPHRESKO-II activities and achieve its future self-sustainably.
- The leadership will comprise a Network Coordinator and Secretariat supported by a wider Network Management Group (NMG) where each member will have responsibility for a specific portfolio.
- The Management (Coordinator and secretariat and NMG) will comprise the current EUPHRESKO-I workpackage leaders (AT-AGES; DE-JKI; FR-DGAL; NL-EL&I; UK-Defra) to ensure continuity during the project, supported by BE-ILVO, DK-DASTI, ES-INIA and PT-INRB; all would be part of overall EUPHRESKO-II Project Management Group. After the end of the project (or possibly during the Project, if part of a test of self-sustainable network management approaches) the NMG membership and that of its supporting implementation/delivery groups might rotate if appropriate.
- The NMG will assign individual responsibilities amongst its members for specific portfolios. Each Portfolio will be led by one NMG member with support as required from other NMG members or additional partners.

WP 2.2. Maintain on-going network activities that underpin trans-national research coordination and collaboration

Against the portfolios listed above, the network will maintain and continue with the following routine activities:

- Mapping of existing and planned projects. Such coordination will ensure optimisation of funds by preventing duplication, allowing potential clustering of projects, and also potential pooling of resources for jointly-funded trans-national activities. This activity will support trans-national research commissioning.
- Advising on plant health priorities for EU Framework Programmes. EUPHRESKO-II will advise the Commission (DG-Research and DG-SANCO) under its COPS mandate. This will enable effective coordination of national, trans-national and EU funding for plant health research.
- Maintaining existing linkages to other plant-health-related activities relevant to EUPHRESKO-II including: links to other EU projects (e.g. ENDURE); links to key stakeholders important to agenda setting (identifying research needs and priorities), e.g. DG SANCO and its Standing Committee on Plant Health; EPPO and its related panels and associated networks (European Mycological Network; European Association of Phytobacteriologists); EFSA and its supporting Plant Health Panel.
- Use and adapt as necessary the pre-existing EUPHRESKO toolbox of processes and tools for implementing trans-national coordination and collaboration, especially for trans-national funding of research.
- Maintaining strategic documents such as the common research strategy frameworks and agendas.

WP 2.3. Evaluate and refine the network model and its modus operandi

- A working group (composed of the 9 members of the EUPHRESKO-2 Project Management Group) will review the network's operational management and implementation annually and propose changes, in discussion with project partners.
- In particular, time inputs by the NMG and other partners supporting it will be recorded to build an accurate picture of the actual time required for the leadership, management and implementation of the network's core activities (portfolios). This will establish the true level of input required to operate the network without any external funding support and inform changes to the network structure and modus operandi.
- Other experiences and models for self-sustainability will also be obtained from other ERA-Nets. Their applicability and potential use in EUPHRESKO will be evaluated, e.g. membership fees, sponsoring tools, etc. If these are found to be needed and applicable, such tools will be developed and incorporated into the final modus operandi.
- The final revised network structure and modus operandi will ensure an effective, efficient and self-sustainable long-term network emerges that is fit-for-purpose.

NMG Scope, Membership and Leadership and Terms of Reference (DL2.1)

NMG 1: Coordinator and secretariat – with responsibility to lead the NMG (UK-Defra). Sub-tasks in this portfolio, are to:

- Manage internal and external communications and serve as a central contact point.
- Oversee the other portfolios (whose chairs will report to the Coordinator) and their timetables, and keep under review (with the NMG) the network structure and *modus operandi* for the long-term network.
- Publish results from trans-national projects and other outputs from EUPHRESKO.
- Maintenance of, the website
- Maintain annual mapping of commissioned and planned national projects and disseminate information on national programmes.

NMG 2: Processes and tools - The portfolio will be governed by a chair (DE-JKI) and a vice-chair (NL-EL&I); sub-tasks can be realised by other NMG members or additional partners. Sub-tasks in this portfolio are to:

- Maintain the common strategic research agenda; including preparation of necessary tools for engagement with wider stakeholders on agenda setting.
- Maintain other required tools necessary for the implementation of joint activities.

NMG 3: Network linkages - The portfolio will be governed by the chair (DE-JKI) and a vice-chair (NL-EL&I); sub-tasks can be realised by other NMG members and/or additional partners. Sub-tasks in this portfolio are to:

- Maintain existing contact with, and advice to, the Commission's DG Research on plant health research priorities in FP7 and subsequently FP8 (under EUPHRESKO's COPHS mandate). Also explore increased linkages to SCAR (Standing Committee on Agricultural Research), especially in the context of collaborative working groups, inputs into foresight activities and infrastructures; and contacts with Joint Programming Initiatives (e.g. FACCE).
- Explore and develop linkages to other EU initiatives (e.g. those from COPHS and DG SANCO; keep linkages to other EU-funded projects that may have a link into EUPHRESKO-II, e.g. Networks of Excellence like ENDURE).
- Ensure appropriate linkages with COST actions, e.g. for agenda setting and to ensure complementarities and added value with trans-national projects from EUPHRESKO. This has already been achieved in the new EUPHRESKO Phytoplasma project that started in 2010 where links and complementarities have been achieved with COST FA0807 on "integrated management of phytoplasma epidemics".
- Maintain appropriate links to Technology Platforms (e.g. Plants for the Future; Forest-based sector). Although TPs are industry led and Plant Health is primarily a statutory activity, possibilities for cooperation exists, especially in sharing and influencing agendas.
- Keep existing contacts to other stakeholders or potential new partners within and outside the EU.

NMG 4: Implementation of joint activities - The portfolio will be governed by the chair (AT-AGES) and the vice-chairs (NL-EL&I, NL-PPS); sub-tasks can be realised by other NMG members and/or additional partners. Sub-tasks in this portfolio are to:

- Initiate and oversee regular rounds for identifying and prioritising trans-national research topics.
- Initiate the process for subsequent joint calls and project commissioning by funding consortia.